

This is an unedited commentary published in *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*.

Please cite as:

Karwowski, M., & Zielińska, A. (2024). Be curious: Strategic curiosity drives creativity. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 47, e104. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X23003412>

Be Curious: Strategic Curiosity Drives Creativity

Maciej Karwowski and Aleksandra Zielińska

University of Wrocław

Authors' Note and Acknowledgements

Maciej Karwowski and Aleksandra Zielińska, Institute of Psychology, University of Wrocław, Poland.

The authors were supported by grants from the National Science Center Poland: Maciej Karwowski (2022/45/B/HS6/00372), Aleksandra Zielińska (2022/45/N/HS6/00625).

Please address correspondence concerning this article to Maciej Karwowski, Institute of Psychology, University of Wrocław, Dawida 1, 50-527 Wrocław, Poland, maciej.karwowski@uwr.edu.pl

Abstract

Ivancovsky, Baror, and Bar provide a compelling argument for the role of curiosity in creative thinking. In this commentary, we go beyond creative cognition and discuss the role of curiosity in real-life creative activities, from hobbyist mundane forms of creativity to professional creative actions. We argue that (a) trait-like curiosity is necessary to engage in creative actions and (b) state-like curiosity might be effectively and strategically induced during interventions. Thus, we posit that curiosity works in an agentic and strategic way in strengthening creativity.

Keywords: strategic curiosity; wise interventions; creative agency

Be Curious: Strategic Curiosity Drives Creativity

One of the greatest minds of all time—Albert Einstein—credited passionate curiosity rather than special talents for his scientific discoveries. While we doubt that curiosity alone would ever suffice to make contributions Einstein made, considering curiosity a powerful driver of creativity goes without saying. Therefore, Ivancovsky and colleagues' review (Ivancovsky, Baror, & Bar, 2023) is ambitious and timely. In this commentary, we offer some additional routes for considering the links between curiosity and creativity, specifically by emphasizing the role of curiosity in creative activity rather than creative thinking.

Curiosity and creativity are broad constructs that surprisingly rarely intersected so far (see Gross et al., 2020). Curiosity is multidimensional—to mention exploratory and deprivation curiosity—and so is creativity. In their feature article, Ivancovsky and colleagues focus exclusively on creative thinking, but real-life creativity requires action, taking unknown and risky routes. A feeling of agency drives such action. When people hold confidence (i.e., feel that they possess the necessary skills to deal with tasks and problems) and consider being creative central to their identity, the chances for engaging in creative activity grow (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). Consequently, we posit that curiosity, mainly exploratory curiosity, plays a vital role in creative agency. Moreover, we see curiosity as an effective strategy for stimulating people's creative engagement. Below, we unpack this reasoning, hoping to enrich Ivancovsky and colleagues' perspectives.

As a recent meta-analysis (Schutte & Malouff, 2020) demonstrated, there are robust links between trait-like curiosity and self-reported creativity ($r = .52$), but a negligible correlation when rated creativity is considered ($r = .16$). Another study (Karwowski, 2012) found a strong latent correlation ($r = .72$) between exploratory curiosity (stretching) and creative self-efficacy and only slightly weaker links between creative self-efficacy and embracing (i.e., accepting unpredictability, $r = .67$). At the same time, there are robust links between creative self-perception and Openness to experience (Karwowski & Lebuda, 2016), and curiosity occupies a prominent place in the structure of Openness (Christensen et al., 2019), so Openness might confound the relationship between curiosity

and self-perceived creativity. In short, however, although studies relying on trait-like self-report measures do not allow for causal conclusions regarding the links between curiosity and creative agency, engaging in creative activity and—consequently—creative accomplishments seem unlikely without exploratory curiosity. Not only are creative writers characterized by a higher level of curious daydreams than non-writers (Zedelius & Schooler, 2021), but there are synergetic effects of creative confidence and intellectual risk-taking (a factor conceptually close to exploratory curiosity) in explaining creative activity and achievement across various domains (Beghetto et al., 2021).

Apart from the role of trait-like curiosity in creative action, studies utilizing micro-longitudinal, dynamic designs show that a large amount of variability in both curiosity (Kashdan et al., 2013; Lydon-Staley et al., 2020) and creative behavior (Karwowski et al., 2017; Silvia et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2022) stems from within- rather than between-person variation. Regardless of people's relatively stable tendencies to engage in novel-seeking behavior, the state of being curious and the engagement in creative activities vary on a daily or even moment-to-moment basis.

Thus, the link between curiosity and creativity is likely reciprocal (see Ma & Wei, 2023). Yet, it is the state of curiosity and its approach-oriented nature that holds the potential to motivate and support actual action. Specifically, as proposed elsewhere (Kashdan & Fincham, 2002), state-like curiosity might serve as a self-regulatory mechanism promoting creative engagement and sustained efforts toward creative goal attainment. However, empirical attempts to test such boosting effects of curiosity are scarce. Apart from experimental designs, we see great potential for examining the curiosity-creativity dynamic link in research that uses experience sampling methodologies. For instance, initial findings have already demonstrated that the state of curiosity predicts next-day creativity among semi-professional creators (Hagtvedt et al., 2019, Study 2). The mechanism where state-like curiosity drives creative engagement has apparent practical implications. Is it possible to make people more willing to engage in creative actions by enhancing their feelings of curiosity?

We propose that the state of being curious might be induced during wise interventions (Walton & Crum, 2021), thus motivating engagement in real-life creative activities. Such interventions

promote or change specific behaviors by providing opportunities to develop a new way of thinking about the self or look at a situation differently. Given the central role of evaluations or appraisals in conceptualizations of curiosity (e.g., Pekrun, 2019; Silvia, 2008), altering what and why people feel curious can effectively and strategically stimulate their creative engagement.

Take, for example, a daily diary intervention (Zielińska et al., 2022), which showed that boosting people's creative confidence and making the importance of creativity more salient results in greater engagement in everyday creative activities. These effects were achieved using brief prompts that—although focused on strengthening creative self-beliefs—also sparked curiosity. For instance, one of the tasks read: *Over the course of today and tomorrow, try to reflect and generate some sensible reasons for being creative. What does this give us? What does it mean for yourself and other people? Whether—and why!—is it worth developing your own and other people's creativity? Try to ask yourself these questions in different situations.* Such prompts, while fostering creative centrality and confidence, likely also increased the intrinsic value of creative functioning and its usefulness (Dubey et al., 2022), promoting curiosity. We believe these kinds of interventions can be a valuable addition to experimental studies, particularly those employing behavioral measures of curiosity (Gross et al., 2020), offering a deeper understanding of the dynamic interplay between creativity and curiosity in real-life contexts.

References

- Beghetto, R. A., Karwowski, M., & Reiter-Palmon, R. (2021). Intellectual risk taking: A moderating link between creative confidence and creative behavior? *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *15*(4), 637–644. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000323>
- Christensen, A. P., Cotter, K. N., & Silvia, P. J. (2019). Reopening Openness to Experience: A Network Analysis of Four Openness to Experience Inventories. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, *101*(6), 574–588. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223891.2018.1467428>
- Dubey, R., Griffiths, T. L., & Lombrozo, T. (2022). If it's important, then I'm curious: Increasing perceived usefulness stimulates curiosity. *Cognition*, *226*, 105193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2022.105193>
- Gross, M. E., Zedelius, C. M., & Schooler, J. W. (2020). Cultivating an understanding of curiosity as a seed for creativity. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, *35*, 77–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2020.07.015>
- Hagtvedt, L. P., Dossinger, K., Harrison, S. H., & Huang, L. (2019). Curiosity made the cat more creative: Specific curiosity as a driver of creativity. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, *150*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2018.10.007>
- Karwowski, M. (2012). Did curiosity kill the cat? Relationship between trait curiosity, creative self-efficacy and creative personal identity. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, *8*(4), 547–558. <https://doi.org/10.5964/ejop.v8i4.513>
- Karwowski, M., & Beghetto, R. A. (2019). Creative behavior as agentic action. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *13*(4), 402.
- Karwowski, M., & Lebuda, I. (2016). The big five, the huge two, and creative self-beliefs: A meta-analysis. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *10*(2), 214–232. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000035>
- Karwowski, M., Lebuda, I., Szumski, G., & Firkowska-Mankiewicz, A. (2017). From moment-to-moment to day-to-day: Experience sampling and diary investigations in adults' everyday

creativity. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 11(3), 309–324.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000127>

Kashdan, T. B., DeWall, C. N., Pond, R. S., Silvia, P. J., Lambert, N. M., Fincham, F. D., Savostyanova, A. A., & Keller, P. S. (2013). Curiosity Protects Against Interpersonal Aggression: Cross-Sectional, Daily Process, and Behavioral Evidence. *Journal of Personality*, 81(1), 87–102.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.2012.00783.x>

Kashdan, T. B., & Fincham, F. D. (2002). “Facilitating creativity by regulating curiosity”: Comment.

American Psychologist, 57(5), 373–374. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.57.5.373>

Lydon-Staley, D. M., Zurn, P., & Bassett, D. S. (2020). Within-person variability in curiosity during daily life and associations with well-being. *Journal of Personality*, 88(4), 625–641.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12515>

Ma, J. (Yonas), & Wei, W. (2023). Curiosity Causes Creativity? Revealing the Reinforcement Circle between State Curiosity and Creativity. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, jocb.606.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.606>

Pekrun, R. (2019). The Murky Distinction Between Curiosity and Interest: State of the Art and Future Prospects. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(4), 905–914. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09512-1>

Schutte, N. S., & Malouff, J. M. (2020). A Meta-Analysis of the Relationship between Curiosity and Creativity. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 54(4), 940–947.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.421>

Silvia, P. J. (2008). Interest—The Curious Emotion. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 17(1), 57–60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2008.00548.x>

Silvia, P. J., Beaty, R. E., Nusbaum, E. C., Eddington, K. M., Levin-Aspensson, H., & Kwapil, T. R. (2014). Everyday creativity in daily life: An experience-sampling study of “little c” creativity.

Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 8(2), 183–188.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035722>

Smith, K., Pickering, A., & Bhattacharya, J. (2022). The Creative Life: A Daily Diary Study of Creativity, Affect, and Well-Being in Creative Individuals. *Creativity Research Journal*, 34(4), 460–479.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2022.2122371>

Walton, G. M., & Crum, A. (Eds.). (2021). *Handbook of wise interventions: How social psychology can help people change*. The Guilford Press.

Zedelius, C. M., & Schooler, J. (2021). *Curious and Fantastical: The Daydreaming of Creative Writers*

[Preprint]. PsyArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/fmve2>

Zielińska, A., Lebuda, I., & Karwowski, M. (2022). Simple, yet wise? Students' creative engagement benefits from a daily intervention. *Translational Issues in Psychological Sciences.*, 8(1), 6–23.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/tps0000289>